

Economy of Remittance Inflows to Pakistan and its Determinants

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Abstract

This research aims to examine and analyzes the effect of transaction cost of remittances on the remittance inflows to Pakistan for the period 2011-2020, it also studies different economic indicators such as exchange rate and inflation that helps in explaining remittances inflows to Pakistan. Only a small number of studies have investigated the macroeconomic factors of remittances inflows to Pakistan. This study will try to fill that gap and at the end suggest policies while keeping in mind the current economic scenario of the country.

1. Introduction

Remittance is a transfer of money from a foreign country by international migrants, diaspora members or family members, to support their family through the earnings workers make abroad. It's recognized to be one of the leading foreign exchange earnings for developing countries like Pakistan, by exporting labor force abroad. Remittances even if entirely consumed results in the betterment and welfare of a society, it has proven to be one of the largest sources of foreign exchange after export inflows. Inflows to Pakistan has more than doubled in the past two decades and there are a lot of key policy measures at play, taken by the government of Pakistan and international stakeholders such as the United Nations in order to achieve sustainable development goal; to decrease the cost of transaction.

Pakistan is a developing country and currently short in supply of foreign exchange reserves, due to which it tends to take loans or depend upon IMF packages to keep the already depreciating currency (rupee) stable. For that, Pakistan exports labor force abroad to keep the inflow of remittances steady but merely doing that does not help in keeping the inflows steady, Remittances inflow depends upon more than one economic indicator such as transaction cost, exchange rate, inflation, technological advancement and migrant outflows. Each and every indicator has to be studied and analyzed in order to make inflow friendly decisions such as the Pakistan remittance initiative established in 2009.

This paper will analyze the main determinants that explains remittances inflows to Pakistan such as the average cost of transaction, exchange rate and technological advancement. Data of the indicators mentioned is taken from the World Development Index (WDI). It is important to understand these determinants in order to further the key measures already and to be taken and make stable Pakistan's foreign exchange reserves to meet the required balance of payments. Most of other studies done on remittances explains different determinants or motives behind sending remittances to Pakistan such as altruism, inheritance or investment approach, certainly lacking the impact of average transaction costs on remittances inflow.

1.1. Research Gap and Problem Statement

The main problem faced in explaining the determinants of remittance inflows to Pakistan is that the data taken from the World Development Indicator does not take in to account the remittances received through *Hundi* or *Hawala* system; one of the main informal corridors used

to transfer funds from a host to home country. If the data is not available, then this paper cannot suggest important policy measures to increase the inflow of remittances to Pakistan.

1.2. Objective of this research

Purpose of this paper is to find the impact of average transaction cost on the remittance inflows to Pakistan.

1.3. Research Question

What is the impact of average transaction cost on remittances inflow to Pakistan?

1.4. Hypothesis

Hypothesis of the study is.

“A decrease in the average transaction cost increases the remittance inflows to Pakistan.”

2. Literature Review

United Nations (2015) sustainable development goal prioritizes that the cost of transaction has to be reduced to less than 3 percent for migrants and eliminate those remittance corridors which has transaction cost higher than five percent. This SDG will have a positive impact for developing countries specially for Pakistan to increase its access to international capital market. moreover, to keep its balance of payments and foreign exchange reserves stable.

Pakistan Remittance Initiative or PRI was launched by the Government of Pakistan in 2008 with an objective to increase the remittances inflow by decreasing the cost of transactions along with encouraging overseas Pakistani's to invest in Pakistan (Rehman, Nasir, Sarwar, and Ahmad, (2019). Rehman et al (2019) found in their study that this initiative taken by the Government was a need of the time and has improved a lot in decreasing the transaction cost of remittances in order to reduce the increasing gap between exports inflows and remittances. According to Rehman et al (2019), comparing the before and after effect of the implementation of PRI, the remittances inflows are now much steeper than it was in 1970's, although there are other indicators involved too besides the transaction cost of remittances, such as migration outflow, economic conditions, altruism and technological advancement in the home and host countries.

Keeping in view the inflow of remittances, Ahmed and Zarzoso (2016) observed that reducing the cost of sending remittances to home countries can be more effective if the level

of immigrants is significant in the host countries, such as the Gulf countries, UK and US. Ahmed and Zarzoso (2016) also highlights the main barriers in remittance inflows for Pakistan such as high transaction costs, time to withdraw their money along with less transaction cost and efficient ways of the informal remittance sector which ultimately tend people to use the informal channels when sending remittances to Pakistan.

The transaction cost of sending remittances depends upon geographical distance between the home and the host countries; longer the distance, higher the transaction costs will be. When Schiopu and Siegfried (2006) studied these indicators by using a panel dataset of bilateral remittances of 21 countries from 2000-2005, they found the opposite and stated that geographical distance does not explain remittance inflows. Ahmed and Zarzoso (2014) took geographical distance as a proxy for cost of remittances, which contradicts with Shiopu and Siegfried's (2006) findings, which states that the cost of remittances does not depend on geographical distance.

Up until now, only one study has examined the main remittance intentions in the context of Pakistan, by Kock and Sun (2011), which suggests that along with transaction cost, the investment return, nominal and real exchange rate, skill level, economic and security conditions also play an important role in explaining remittances to Pakistan

In previous research done by Freund and Spatafora (2008), on determinants of remittances and related transaction cost of sending remittances for 10 developing countries, found that transaction cost has a negative effect and exchange rate has a positive effect on remittances, that is if the currency depreciates, and inflation rises then the labor force working abroad transfers more money to help their families during inflation, ultimately making the GNP to increase along with the remittance inflows.

In a detailed study done by Qureshi (2016) on Pakistan Remittances Initiative (PRI) and its aftereffects highlighted a significant increase in formal remittance flows to Pakistan. His research, based on the data collected from the State bank of Pakistan, found that remittance flow to Pakistan has significantly increased by 13 percent due to the SDG implemented by Pakistan in terms of PRI, and migrants are shifting from *Hundi* (informal channel) towards using formal channels to send remittances to Pakistan.

3. Methodology

3.1. Theoretical Framework

Theoretically, there is a credible bond between the transaction cost and the amount sent, the hypothesis stated above appeals to the basic microeconomic principles that a remitter should be sensitive to the cost and behave accordingly, that is to send less if the prices are high and more if the prices are low. The findings stated in the literature review above also furthers an inverse relationship between the cost and the amount sent. However, the empirical model focuses more on the micro-economic indicators and their impact on remittances. Moreover, there are other possible indicator that explains remittances inflow to Pakistan, such as technology and migration outflows, but those indicators are not included in the model stated below.

Dependent Variable

Personal Remittances Received:

Personal remittances received consists of all the transfers made by nonresident from a host country and received by households in the home country.

Independent Variables

Average Transaction Cost of sending remittances to Pakistan:

Average transaction cost of sending remittances is the average of the total transaction cost charged by remittance service provider in percentage on the amount per 200 US dollars sent through formal channels.

Exchange Rate:

Official Exchange rate refers to exchange rate calculated by the official authorities of the state or determined by the legal exchange market; Pakistan rupees relative to U.S dollars (annually).

Inflation:

Inflation measured by the consumer price index reflects the annual change in percentage in the cost of buying a basket of goods and services yearly.

3.2. Data Description

Secondary data for this study was collected from the World Development Indicator for the period 2011-2020. Table below shows the variables, Units and sources of the data used. Time series data was collected to find out the impact of average transaction cost of remittances on the inflow of remittances to Pakistan. Log is taken for data of personal remittances received and imported in STATA in terms of millions.

Variables	Unit	Source
Dependent Variable		
Personal Remittances received	Current US\$ (in millions)	WDI
Independent Variables		
Average transaction cost of sending remittances to Pakistan	Percentage of cost per 200 U.S dollars sent to Pakistan	WDI
Exchange rate	LCU per US\$, period average	WDI
Inflation	Consumer prices (annual %)	WDI

Table 3.1: Data, Units and Sources.

3.3. Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs	Mean	St. Deviation	Min	Max	SKW	KUR
Remittances received	10	2015.5	3.02765	2011	2020	0.0707	2.259
Exchange rate	10	18667.7	4200.631	12263	2610	1.0637	2.753
Av. Transaction cost	10	5.194985	0.7588763	4.019404	6.587	0.2912	2.327
Inflation	10	7.225622	3.237306	2.529328	11.91	-0.0489	1.613

Table 3.2: Descriptive statistics

3.4. Empirical Model

OLS (Ordinary Least Square) method is used to see and analyze the impact of average transaction cost of sending remittances to Pakistan on personal remittances received. The model mentioned below also contains other important indicators that play a vital role in explaining remittances to Pakistan.

$$\text{Personal remittances received} = f(\text{Avg. transaction cost, Exchange rate, Inflation})$$

In the model, Personal remittances received is the dependent variable and a function of average transaction cost (ATC), Exchange rate (E) and Inflation (I).

$$\text{Personal remittances received} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \text{ ATC} + \beta_2 \mathcal{E} + \beta_3 \text{ I} + \mu_i$$

Where,

α = Intercept

β = Regression Coefficient of variables

μ_i = Random Error

ATC = Average transaction cost of remittances sent to Pakistan

\mathcal{E} = Exchange rate

I = Inflation rate

4. Results and Discussion

Linear regression

	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Remittancesreceived							
Avgtransactioncost	-969.504	643.012	-1.51	.182	-2542.898	603.889	
Exchangerate	145.825	20.065	7.27	0	96.727	194.923	***
Inflation	-476.549	113.335	-4.20	.006	-753.869	-199.229	***
Constant	10718.829	4874.524	2.20	.07	-1208.702	22646.36	*
Mean dependent var		18667.700	SD dependent var			4200.631	
R-squared		0.969	Number of obs			10	
F-test		61.835	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		167.553	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			168.764	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Table 4.1: OLS Regression Table

	(1) Remittancesreceived
Avgtransactionc~t	-969.504 (643.012)
Exchangerate	145.825*** (20.065)
Inflation	-476.549*** (113.335)
_cons	10718.829* (4874.524)
Observations	10
R-squared	.969

Standard errors are in parentheses

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Table 4.2: Nested Regression Table

Results stated above demonstrates that the overall model is significant, since the Prob > F is less than 0.05. R-squared value of 0.9687 shows that 96 percent of the change in dependent variable is depicted by independent variables.

$$\text{Remittances received} = 10718.83 + (-969.5044) \text{ ATC} + 145.82 \text{ } \mathcal{E} + (-476.54) \text{ I}$$

Results for the OLS regression shows us the impact of average transaction cost of remittances on total remittances received in Pakistan. Coefficient for the Avg. transaction cost shows us that there is a negative or inverse relationship between ATC and remittances received in Pakistan, moreover, findings from the OLS regression demonstrates that a 1 unite change in average transaction cost will increase the remittances by 9.69%, or a decrease in ATC by 1 unit (sending per 200\$) will increase the remittances by 969.5044 dollars (in millions). Ahmed and Zarzoso (2014) had also stated a negative relationship between ATC and remittance inflows to Pakistan, which also furthers my take on to the hypothesis stated above. However, the P-value for ATC demonstrates an alternate; $P > |t|$ value of 0.182 and reveals that the impact of ATC on remittances is insignificant or there maybe 18 percent chance that the null hypothesis is correct.

Graph 4.1: Two-way scatter plot(l-fit) of remittances received and avg. transaction cost.

The average transaction cost of sending remittances plays an important role in defining remittance inflows to Pakistan, migrants will send more money if the cost of sending is low and less money if the cost of sending is high.

According to the coefficient of Exchange rate, there's a positive relation between remittances inflow and exchange rate, which Freund and Spatafora (2008) also found in their study on the data taken for 10 developing countries. OLS result stated above demonstrates that a 1-unit change in exchange rate will cause the remittance inflows to Pakistan to increase by 145.827 dollars (in millions). One of the main arguments behind the impact of Exchange rate on remittances is that if the value of rupee depreciates, then people will send more money from abroad to enjoy the perks keeping in view the before and after effect of rupee depreciation. Certainly, people will tend to send more money in to Pakistan now that their families are receiving more money while withdrawing the money sent from abroad.

Freund and Spatafora (2008) also found in their study that inflation plays an important role while explaining remittances to developing countries and concluded a negative relationship between remittance and inflation. According to the coefficient of inflation as stated above, there's a negative relationship between inflation and remittances, a 1-unit change in inflation will decrease remittances by 476.5494 or by 4.76 percent. If the inflation rate decreases migrants will send less money and if the inflation rate increases, migrants will send more money to help their family in going through inflation and help them to fulfil their basic needs.

4.1. Diagnostic Tests and Analysis

Different tests were conducted for this model. I applied VIF test to see multicollinearity among variables, the outcome value of this result was $2.20 < 10$, which states that no multicollinearity was observed among the independent variables. Second, Breusch-Pagan test was conducted to see whether residuals are distributed with equal variance at each level of the predictor variable or not? The outcome or P-value of this result was $0.32 > 0.05$, which shows that there is no heteroscedasticity present in the data. Third, the value for the D-Watson test 1.67 shows a positive autocorrelation, and states that an increase during a time interval results in an increase in lagged time interval; the remittances tend to increase when they are increasing and tend to decrease when they are decreasing.

5. Conclusion and Policy Recommendation

This study examines the impact of average transaction cost of remittances on the remittances inflows to Pakistan by using yearly data for the period 2011-2020, OLS regression technique is used to check the relationship between dependent variables and independent variables. The result shows that Avg. transaction cost has a negative yet insignificant impact on the

remittances inflows to Pakistan. One percent decrease in ATC increases remittances inflows to Pakistan by 9.69 percent. Pakistan is a developing country and currently short in supply of foreign exchange reserves due to the increasing gap between exports and imports, and at this hour of need, remittances from abroad can be the only rational supply of forex that Pakistan can easily opt for rather than depending on foreign aid or loans. Remittances does not only stabilize the foreign exchange reserves of Pakistan but also brings welfare along itself. By implementing United Nations SDG for decreasing transaction cost of remittances to less than 3 percent will not only help Pakistan to overcome the need for loans but also stabilize its depreciating currency. One of the main factors that can play an important, yet negative, role if the Pakistan Remittance Initiative is not implemented properly is that the migrants will move towards using informal channels to send remittances to Pakistan, which will ultimately result in loss for the national exchequer. Keeping this in view, Pakistan should also consider lowering the ATC of sending remittances in order to keep people at a distance from using informal corridors. The Hawala or Hundi system is also on the radar of Financial Action task Force (FATF) because of the illegal money sent and received, and Pakistan being on the grey list should incentivize to reduce ATC so that migrants should opt for legal channels while sending money to Pakistan, this will not only benefit the national exchequer but also make Pakistan to comply with FATF.

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Appendix

Graph: Two-way scatter plot of remittances received and exchange rate.

Graph: Two-way scatter plot of remittances received and inflation.